

Speculation on the Meaning of the Kaniadakis $\ln_k(p)$ for Small k

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In the Shannon case, $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ for $p(e_i)$ unnormalized. In the Kaniadakis case, one has instead: $\ln_k(p(e_i)) = 1/2k \{ p(e_i)^k - p(e_i)^{-k} \} = -e_i/T$. Again, $p(e_i)$ is unnormalized. We suggest that the meaning of $\ln_k(p(e_i))$ may be a little obscure because of the two powers k and $-k$, with $0 < k < 1$ and investigate a possible interpretation for $k \ll 1$. For $k=0$, $\ln_k(p) = \ln(p)$.

In (1), it is pointed out that $\ln_k(p) = \ln(p) \text{Product}_{j=1, \text{infinite}} [1 + u_j / (j \cdot 3.14 \cdot 3.14)]$ ((1)) where $u = k \ln(p)$. If one considers $k \ll 1$, then $\ln_k(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i)) \exp(-kk \ln(p) \ln(p) / 6)$. The second factor is an unnormalized Gaussian in the variable $\ln(p)$. In Shannon's theory, $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4)$ and $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$, so one may take \ln of the first equation and equate it to the second. This leads to $p(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)$ unnormalized which leads to a very rapid drop-off for high e_i/T . We speculate here that the Kaniadakis approach for $k \ll 1$ implies that instead of using $\ln(p)$ linked with p in $p(e_1)p(e_2)$, there is a statistical Gaussian which weights $\ln(p)$ and so has an affect on different $\ln(p(e_i))$ values. Thus, $\ln(p) \exp(-kk \ln(p) \ln(p) / 6)$ may suggest that $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ for a reaction is too idealized and that there is a Gaussian weighting factor (representing randomness in $\ln(p)$) which applies.

We examine the resulting effects on $p(e_i)$ and show that for large e_i/T , $p(e_i)$ does not drop-off as quickly as $\exp(-e_i/T)$.

Shannon Case

In the Shannon case, information $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ ((2)) for $p(e_i)$ unnormalized. This leads to:

$p(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)$ unnormalized which drops off very quickly as e_i/T becomes large.

If one uses action-reaction balance, then:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4) \quad ((3b))$$

If one takes \ln of $p(e_i)$ unnormalized and equates to a constant multiplied by ((3a)) then:
 $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ ((4))

Thus, $\ln(p(e_i))$ as a representation of information seems to be based on a $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ reaction probability which leads to a very rapid drop in e_i/T in $\exp(-e_i/T)$. If one suggests that perhaps $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ is not the correct probability for a reaction and that high e_i/T should be enhanced because they represent particles which move very quickly and should have a better chance to interact than a slow moving particle because they encounter more targets in the same period of time, then the question then becomes: How should this be quantified?

Kaniadakis Case

The Kaniadakis case differs from the Shannon case in that one has:

$$-e_i/T = \ln_k(p(e_i)) = 1/2k \{ p(e_i)^k - p(e_i)^{-k} \} \quad ((5)) \text{ with } p(e_i) \text{ unnormalized}$$

Shannon's information $\ln(p)$ is now given by $\ln_k(p)$ and it is somewhat difficult to interpret the meaning of ((5)) in terms of $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ as a two body scattering reaction probability.

In (1), it is pointed out that:

$$\ln_k(p) = \ln(p) \prod_{j=1, \infty} [1 + u u / (j^2 3.14^2)] \quad ((6)) \text{ where } u = k \ln(p).$$

If one takes the $k \ll 1$ limit, then:

$$\ln_k(p) = \ln(p(e_i)) \exp(-k k \ln(p) \ln(p) / 6) \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{This follows because: } \sum_i 1 / (n^i) = 3.14^2 / 6. \quad (2)$$

To verify that ((7)) is correct, one may expand $1/2k (p^k - p^{-k})$ to third order (or more) and compare with the expansion of ((7)). The two agree.

We suggest that ((7)) may have a statistical interpretation because ((7)) is a Gaussian in the variable $\ln(p)$. Gaussians are associated with maximum random information. Thus, instead of using $\ln(p(e_i))$ to find $-e_i/T$, $\ln(p(e_i))$ is taken as a variable which is multiplied by a Gaussian factor for $k \ll 1$. In other words, it is not $\ln(p(e_i))$ by itself which gives the physical information $-e_i/T$.

We suggest that even though the Kaniadakis $\ln_k(p(e_i))$ form is perhaps difficult to interpret physically or statistically, ((7)) may be more readily interpreted. The point then is that one could write ((7)) a priori and suggest that for a parameter $k \ll 1$, one has the statistical picture of ((7)). The question then would be finding an appropriate form for k not being small, but at least ((7)) provides a statistical view of how $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ changes for $k \ll 1$.

Kaniadakis $\ln_k(p)$

We consider the $\ln_k(p)$ form ((5)) versus $\ln(p)$ for $k = .5$ and $p = 1/6, 1/3, 1/2$.

$$\ln(.5) = -.69 \quad \ln_k(.5) = -.686 \quad \text{fractional change: } .58\%$$

$$\ln(.333) = -1.089 \quad \ln_k(.333) = -1.11 \quad \text{fractional change: } 1.8\%$$

$$\ln(1/6) = -1.79 \quad \ln_k(1/6) = -2.04 \quad \text{fractional change: } 14\%$$

Thus \ln_k returns higher probabilities for the same $-e_i/T$, i.e. there is not such a sharp drop-off for e_i/T becoming large as in $\exp(-e_i/T)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the $k \ll 1$ limit of the Kaniadakis $\ln_k(p)$ to see if one may find a physical or statistical interpretation which is difficult to see in the full form of $\ln_k(p)$. We find $\ln(p) \exp(-k \ln(p) \ln(p)/6)$ for $k \ll 1$ which suggests a statistical unnormalized Gaussian factor multiplied by $\ln(p)$. This suggests that $p(e_i)p(e_j)$, used in Shannon's entropy calculation, may be too idealized. Instead of using $\ln(p)$, one treats it as a variable which may be part of a Gaussian (random) distribution and uses $\ln(p) \exp(-k \ln(p) \ln(p)/6)$. We suggest that this may be a statistical interpretation for $k \ll 1$ which could be introduced a priori and may allow one to interpret $\ln_k(p)$.

References

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